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THE CAPABILITY APPROACH: ITS RECENT DEVELOPMENTS AND A CRITIQUE

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ABSTRACT

An attempt has been made in this paper to discuss the basic ideas of the Capability Approach; To show how it has been applied by many scholars to study the various problems relating to human well being as well as to evaluate the existing public policies; What are the recent trends or contribution of several scholars to the Capability Approach and to discuss the various criticisms of the Capability Approach.

Key words: *Capability, scholars, human, public policies*

"The primary goods approach seems to take little note of the diversity of human beings... If people were basically very similar then an index of primary goods might be quite a good way of judging advantage. But, in fact people seem to have very different needs varying with health, longevity, climate conditions, temperament and even body size... So, what is being involved is not merely ignoring a few hard cases, but overlooking very widespread and real differences".

-Amartya Sen

Introduction:

The Capability Approach (CA) of Amartya Sen has emerged as a new, alternative theoretical framework about human well-being, economic development, equality and justice. Although some of the basic ideas of CA can be traced back to Aristotle, Adam Smith and Karl Marx and the contemporary influences of likes of Rawls, Stewart & Streetan, the C.A has actually been conceptualized by Amartya Sen as an alternative to the traditional welfare economics which equates well being with either commodities or utility. According to Sen, even though economic growth and expansion of goods and services are necessary for human development these are not sufficient. For evaluation of economic development in any country we must consider as to whether people are able to achieve what they value and want to achieve.

Following Sen, many others have developed the CA, and it has found many supporters. The strength of the CA is said to be its flexibility, internal pluralism and interdisciplinary outlook whereas the critics have pointed out that the framework put forth by Sen is too idealistic, incomplete and difficult to operationalize.

Yet, in the two decades since Amartya Sen first introduced the concept of CA in 1979 in the Tanner lectures, 'Equality of what' there has been a lot of new research using CA, especially by younger scholars. The Capability Approach has been used by academicians, governments and NGO's to assess various issues relating to economic development, equality, and justice as also to define and evaluate the public policy, both in the developed and developing countries. The United Nation Development programme (UNDP) has, now adopted

the Human Development Index for evaluating and comparing the performance of different countries using the indicators developed by the CA pioneers.

An attempt has been made in this study to understand the basic ideas of the Capability Approach; To show how it has been applied by many scholars to study the various problems relating to human well-being as well as to evaluate the existing public policies; The recent trends or contribution of several scholars to the CA and to discuss the various criticisms of the CA.

The Concept:

The CA was developed by Amartya Sen to study development and justice on the premise that resources and utilities, by themselves, cannot ensure wellbeing of humankind, as envisaged by the resourcist and utility theorists. What is important according to Sen, is the freedom to achieve well-being and this freedom to achieve well-being is to be understood in terms of people's capabilities where capability means their real opportunities to do and to be what they have reason to value.

The **core ideas** that form the basis of Amartya Sen's CA are '**Functionings**' and '**Capabilities**'. **Functionings** are a person's or group's 'beings' and 'doings', which they have, reason to value. e.g. being educated or being well nourished are 'beings' which can be achieved by the 'doing' of studying in a good school, eating a healthy diet and so on.

Functionings can be most basic or elementary like food, health, and shelter or advanced like having a self-fulfilling job, leisure etc. In short, functionings are those beings and doings of a human being, which make his life more human and valuable. It is important to note that the distinction between beings and doings is sometime blurred and that these are morally neutral.

A **functioning set** on the other hand are a person's or groups overall state of well-being. It is the sum total of multiple functionings. The functionings vary among persons, group and societies depending upon various social, political, culture, environmental and other factors.

Capabilities are the real freedoms or opportunities to achieve the valuable functionings. Thus, while being educated and going to a good school are a person's functionings, real opportunity of proper schooling is the corresponding capability. Therefore Capability is a person's ability to achieve a valued functioning. For achieving a functioning set (e.g. a particular lifestyle), the person will require a bundle of capabilities called a capability set to choose from. This freedom to choose is vital to Sen's conception of CA as he states "expansion of freedom is viewed both (1) the primary end and (2) the principal means of development". In this regard Sen identifies **five instrumental freedoms** which are valuable not only as ends in themselves but also as the primary means of development i.e. political freedoms, economics facilities, social opportunities, transparency guarantees and protective security.

According to the CA, 'functioning' and 'capabilities' are the best metric for evaluating development and making interpersonal comparisons rather than incomes, commodities and utility. The CA places human beings at the centre stage of socio-economic development and by focusing on capabilities rather than functionings in social evaluation; it brings forth the concern of human freedoms. This brings us to the next crucial concept of Agency. **Agency** implies that an individual acts in terms of his own values and objectives because Sen is of the view that "The people have to be seen, in this perspective, as being actively involved- given the opportunity- in shaping their own destiny, and not just as passive recipients of the fruits of cunning development programmes"¹

Freedom of choice is central to leading a good life therefore, it is an integral part of Amartya Sen's Capability Approach. In CA we are concerned with instrumental role of freedom. For example, what living standard we can enjoy must depend how free we are to choose one bundle of commodities rather than another. However, this importance of instrumental freedom (as means to an end) does not entail a denial of intrinsic importance of

freedom (an end in itself) However, in the general tradition of economics its instrumental role is much more prominent than its intrinsic role. There are two ways of viewing freedom i.e. positive freedom or what a person can choose to do or be and negative freedom which emphasizes on absence of any class of restraints that a person or institution may exercise over another. To differentiate between the two freedoms, an example is given of a person who is hungry because of low wages or unemployment. But, no one has stopped him from going to work or forced him to accept low wages. Then, his negative freedom has not been violated and is rather, protected. On the other hand, his positive freedom from hunger is compromised by circumstances.

After Sen, there have been several attempts to enlarge, augment & clarify the various aspects of the CA. Most important among these are by Robeyns, Clark, Alkire and Nussbaum. Some scholars like Nussbaum have generated lists of capabilities while others have devised methodologies to implement the capability framework for conducting empirical studies.

The most important attempt to build-upon the Capability Approach can be seen in the writings of the feminist philosopher, Martha Nussbaum. Drawing inspiration from Aristotle, she has developed a definite list of 10 'central human capabilities' namely (1) Life, (2) Bodily Health, (3) Bodily Integrity, (4) Senses imagination and thought, (5) Emotions, (6) Practical reason, (7) Affiliation, (8) Other species, (9) Play and (10) Political and material control of one's environment.

Nussbaum (Nussbaum& Martha , 2000), has selected the above central human capabilities because these are the human capabilities that can be convincingly argued to be of central importance in any human life, whatever else the person pursues or chooses. Nussbaum has stated that this list is subject to revision, yet in the last decade, there has not been any addition or deletion in the list. However, Amartya Sen has consistently refused to defend any one pre-determined canonical list of capabilities, chosen by theorists without any general social discussion or public reasoning³. Instead, he has advocated a more direct approach for collecting information about the human values placing reliance on the constructive role of democracy and importance of public participation, discussion and debate. The selection of capabilities, according to Sen will depend upon the purpose of the studying, social conditions and priorities etc.

Recent Developments:

In the three decades since CA was first introduced by Amartya Sen, there has emerged a plethora of literature where CA has been used to study the issues of development, equality, policy making, quality of life, justice, etc, in different parts of the world, developed as well as developing. Ingrid Robeyns⁴ has surveyed the vast literature and grouped them under the following themes:

- General Assessments of the Human Development of a Country

Initially, Sen himself had presented the comparative chart of GNP per-capita and functioning performance like life expectancy and infant mortality of Brazil, China, India, Mexico, Oman and Sri Lanka to show that rankings of countries based on GNP per- capita is quite different from rankings based on the selected functionings. Since then, the UNDP has adopted some of the selected functionings developed by Amartya Sen and Mahbubul Haq to prepare a Human Development Index (HDI) for measuring & comparing the performance of different countries. In fact, every year the Human Development Report also focuses on a particular theme of development like globalization, new technologies, human rights, gender issues, etc which are not purely economic criteria but which can be seen more as the expansion of people's capabilities.

Several other scholars have also used the HDI and CA to evaluate Government policies for development and their achievement, most notable being (Dreze& Sen, 2002) who have analysed India's development using the CA.

- Assessing Small Scale Development Projects

Some scholars have used the capability framework for assessing small scale development projects in the developing countries, e.g. Sabina Alkire has assessed the goat rearing, female literacy classes and rose garland production projects in Pakistan to see as to how far these were capability enhancing and compared her findings with monetary evaluations. She found that the goat rearing activity was a sound economic investment though the rate of return largely depended on women's shadow wages. Its economic benefits as per the cost benefit analysis were quantifiable and impressive yet, there were other benefits which were not quantifiable like acquisition of useful knowledge and friendships among women which were valuable for them. Thus, in this project the economic & social achievements were both beneficial. However, the results were different for female literacy classes. In terms of cost benefit analysis, there were no benefits because of lack of opportunities for female employment in these areas. Yet, it benefited the women in other ways as they learnt that women were equal to men and that they need not suffer abuse and most important, they were able to solve some of their problems on their own. There was a feeling of satisfaction. As for the rose cultivation project, it was observed that in economic terms there was a negative internal rate of return but there were significant non-economic benefits. She concludes that in pure economic terms, a comparison of the three projects may conclude that the goat rearing project is superior to the other projects, but the literacy classes have strong impact on knowledge and empowerment, from a capability perspective, no project is superior to other in totality, and "the choice cannot be made on technical grounds but rather is a morally significant choice" (Alkire 2002 pg. 286)

Solava S. & Ibrahim (2006) has used the CA to extend the freedom and agency concepts in the context of self-help groups so that they can enhance their individual capabilities in the given social structures. As a group their bargaining power increases and this results in enhanced collective freedoms and agency. He has provided the example of the ensuing collective capabilities through three case studies of self-help initiatives amongst the poor in Egypt.

- Identifying the Poor in Developing Countries

Traditionally the poor have been identified in terms of monetary terms alone using the World Banks yardstick of a dollar a day (or as in India, Rs. 32 per day) but Caterina Ruggeri Laderchi⁷ used data from Chile to investigate whether income based criteria can capture the basic functionings like education, health and child nutrition and she found that the income variable is not able to show/ explain the shortfall in education, health and child nutrition. Similarly, analyzing data from Peru she found that not all functioning poor are income poor and vice-versa.

In another study Ruggeri Laderchi, Saith & Stewart⁸ compared the four approaches to poverty measurement namely the monetary, capability, social exclusion and participatory approaches and came to the conclusion that the monetary approach gives a false impression of being most accurate and objective. In fact, each approach involves numerous judgments, which are not transparent. As a result the number of people identified as poor by these approaches in turn affects the choice of poverty reduction strategies.

The CA has also been used to estimate the number of poor in the world. Thomas Pogge and Sanjay Reddy (2003) have made an attempt to estimate the number of global poor on the basis of their capabilities. Strongly criticizing monetary estimates, they suggest that global poverty estimates should be based on capabilities. Mohammad Asali, Sanjay Reddy & Sujata Visari have tried to calculate the number of global poor by using the World Bank one dollars a day and two dollars a day poverty lines and compare it with a poverty line based on a set of income dependent elementary capabilities like minimal requirement of calorie intake and non calorie needs and they concluded that national poverty estimates and the ranking of countries differ depending upon which poverty concept one uses. However, for preparing reliable estimates of global poverty, better data and international coordinated effort will be required.

Building on capability approach Siddiqui Rahaman Osmani (2005) has expressed that CA can be seen as a bridge between poverty and human rights as poverty can be defined as denial of human rights. The restricting of human rights should be for a greater cause and restricted in some well defined ways. It should not be seen as inconsistent with the principle of indivisibility of human rights.

- Poverty and well being Assessment in Advanced Economies

Contrary to general impression, CA studies are not just limited to studying poverty in the developing countries. In fact, studies have also been undertaken in developed countries. Alessandro Balestrino (1996) has done a capability study in Italy to analyze whether the officially declared poor people are functioning poor (in terms of education, health, nutrition, etc) or income poor or both. The research indicates that a sizeable number of poor in advanced economies / rich countries are not income poor but functioning poor for whom kind transfers would be more useful than cash transfers.

In another similar study, Shelly Phipps (2002) has made a comparison of well being of children aged 0-11 in Canada, Norway and the USA considering household incomes and a set of ten functionings. She has found that even though the average incomes are similar in the three countries, Norwegian children are better off than Canadian children and that the Canadian and USA functionings cannot be ranked.

- Deprivation of Disabled People

Asghar Zaidi and Tania Burchardt (2005) have used standard techniques in welfare economics to show that the disabled need more income to reach the same levels of material well-being.

Wiebke Kuklys' (2005) study has also confirmed the findings by Zaidi and Burchardt showing that all other things being equal, disabled people in Britain need 44% more income to achieve the same well being in comparison to a not disabled individual.

Reindal (2010) while discussing about special education from a capability perspective, has tried to explain the purpose of 'inclusion' in a theoretical framework. Under the framework, inclusion is to be understood in three ways: epistemological, ontological and ethical and socio-political. This would enable adequate explanation and understanding of disability and the need for inclusion in the special education schemes.

- Assessing Gender Inequalities

Amartya Sen had examined gender inequalities and discrimination in India and he found that in functionings like mortality rates, malnutrition and morbidity women were poor achievers *vis-à-vis*

men. There is a vast literature on missing women which shows that women are denied the most crucial capability- the capability of living (when female fetuses are aborted in India). The CA has also been used to study gender discrimination in advanced

countries e.g. Enrica Chiappero-Martinetti's (2003) study in Italy and Robeyns' (2006) study of gender inequality in Europe.

Alejandro Agudo Sanchez (2010) has examined a particular type of anti-poverty aid- the Mexican Oportunidades Programme and its implications for gender inequality. The author has evaluated the effectiveness of the programme using the CA and this exercise revealed that there was a significant failure to address women's own needs by development schemes which were aimed at poverty rather than inequality reduction.

- Debating Policies

The CA has been used to evaluate government policies also. Thus in Belgium

Eric Schokkaert and Luc Van Ootegem (1990) have found that compensation provided by the State to the unemployed does not help in removing their functionings deprivation. Similar findings have been reported by Hartley Dean and his colleagues who are of the view that the European Employment Strategy is not aimed at expanding people's capabilities rather, it aims to improve people's human capital. While evaluating educational policies,

Lorella Terzi (2005) has argued that CA can be used to address the problems of special needs education.

Omkarnath (2005) has discussed how to operationalize CA in large agrarian economies such as India. CA has limitations in terms of accounting for the formation of capabilities and Sen's reliance on Walrasian modes of analysis is inadequate. The author has attempted to give an alternative framework based on income generation process which can be used by the policy makers to transform the lives of the poor and marginalized in a large agrarian economy.

- Assessing and criticizing social norms

Studies have been conducted using CA to assess and critique social norms and practices. It has been established that social norms may cause certain behaviors that restrict people's capability sets or privileges. Looking from this viewpoint Robeyns asks whether some success stories of economic globalization will remain positive if one looks beyond increases in personal incomes and GNP per capita and takes social and psychological functionings into account. Example- in Philippines, income is generated by women domestic helps working in rich countries, which is good from a traditional economic growth model but there is evidence that such economic migration is harmful to the social relations and mental health of the immigrant worker and the children who are left behind. A functioning evaluation of such migration flows is not as positive as in the purely monetary assessment.

Smith and Seward (2009) have tried to elaborate further on the nature of social factors that influence capabilities as initially stated by Sen. They have argued that the individuals capabilities are the product of individual level capacities and their relative position *vis-à-vis* the prevailing social structures which broadly define their behavior in a given situation.

- Functioning and Capabilities as Concepts in Non- normative Research

Mary Arends-Kuenning and Sajeda Amin (2001) have used the capability concept for ethnographic research in Bangladesh to study whether the rural Bangladeshis perceive women's education as capabilities or as human capital. They found that the majority considered women's education as human capital; there was a minority who saw it as a capability for women's well-being and agency.

In another recent development, Ilse Oosterlaken (2011) has stated that technological artifacts besides social structures and individuals are an important constituent of CA. Ilse Oosterlaken (IO) has based his arguments on the writings by Smith and Seward (S&S), Martins and Lawson. Technology helps in expanding valuable human capabilities. For example, prefabricated houses used during disaster help preserve 'bodily health', telephones enable social interaction and help expand the capability of 'affiliation', etc. Technology artifacts do not exist in isolation but there are interdependencies between technology, social structures and individual as each impact on the other in their own way. However, technology can also be disabling in the attainment of valued functionings. The best technology for developed nations may not thus be suited for the marginalized sections in the developing countries since societies are at different stages of development. Hence the several examples of failed technological transfer to the developing nations.

Rafael Ziegler (2010) has applied the CA approach to discuss Schumpeterian political economy and human development. Using the CA he has proposed two hypotheses to explain innovation for social change:

- Social innovation is the carrying out of a new combination of capabilities and,
- To carry out these new social innovations, there will emerge social entrepreneurs which shall act as agents of change.

Thus he has proposed a synthesis of human development and Schumpeterian development for looking at innovation.

Critique:

The CA has been criticized for many reasons. Sometimes the key strength itself has been portrayed as a potential weakness. The most common criticism is whether Sen's concept of CA is operational or not. However, the large number of empirical researches carried out using CA is a testimony to the fact that the apprehensions are misplaced. There is also a criticism regarding the listing/selection of capabilities and the construction of the capability set. There is also disagreement about the valuation of capabilities and how to assign relative weights.

However, Sen has consistently rejected any attempt of listing a predetermined list of capabilities and with good reason. The selection of capabilities should depend upon the purpose of the exercise and the context at hand. Moreover he is in favour of a more direct approach for the selection of capabilities in a democratic manner on the basis of public discussion and debate. Many capability scholars have tried to respond to this criticism by putting forth certain lists of capabilities which can also be quantified. However, Sen has maintained that:

"The problem is not with listing important capabilities, but with insisting on one predetermined canonical list of capabilities, chosen by theorists without any general

social discussion or public reasoning. To have such a fixed list, emanating entirely from pure theory, is to deny the possibility of fruitful public participation on what should be included and why...public discussion and reasoning can lead to a better understanding of the role, reach and significance of particular capabilities..."
Sen Amartya, (2004)

Another criticism is with regard to CA in practice. The survey studies or involvement of the participants/target individuals or groups. While evaluating public policies the questionnaire or methodology used for the survey may suffer from the bias of those who are conducting it. Since such surveys are not totally objective, the results or the conclusions would thus remain relatively subjective and so CA has to live with it. However, one should note that there is nothing like hundred percent objectivity. The important distinction is that CA is a normative approach and any evaluative exercise (be it of any form) is not free from the above problem.

Scholars like Qizilbash and Carter have criticized CA for underplaying the importance of negative freedom. They are of the view that in some respects negative freedom will feature more prominently while distinguishing internal capabilities from the external conditions required to achieve the given capabilities.

This criticism arises from the fact that in traditional economic theory, it is the negative perspective of freedom that is dominant. Sen has defended his emphasis on positive freedom because the positive characterization of freedom is coherent and it corresponds closely to a person being free to choose.

Apart from the above, there is another criticism where Sen argues that absence of violations of negative freedom can coexist with terrible hardships and miseries in the lives of those who are powerless. Sen explains this phenomenon by citing the following example:

“Many of the major famines in the modern world have taken place in situations of relatively good and undiminished food availability-sometimes even peak food availability-with particular occupation groups (such as landless rural laborers, pastoralists, fishermen) being driven to the wall because of the collapse of their entitlements, despite guaranteed negative freedoms. Thus there is something totally inadequate in focusing on negative freedoms only, and there is clearly a case for paying attention to the overall freedoms i.e, a person being able to do this or be that...” (Sen, Amartya 1987)

Besides this issue of negative-positive freedom, some scholars feel that it is impractical to apply CA for the formulation of policies at the macro level because the informational requirements for CA are extremely high. Acquiring data on multiple functionings is difficult. Moreover, information about some relevant social indicators isn't available. Moving from functioning to capability complicates the exercise further because apart from information on actual choice, additional information is required on counterfactual choices which cannot be observed.

Some also hold CA to be susceptible to the problem of adaptive preferences and cultural indoctrination. However, this criticism does not hold good since empirical studies have shown that the presence of these have not distorted the responses. Also Sen's notion of deliberative democracy is considered to be too idealistic.

Some critics have stated that Sen has not given due importance to the role of power and its dynamic nature; The CA fails to account for the dynamics of political power-decisions which undermine the democratic process and hence capabilities. For example, political power in a society may be concentrated in the hands of a few rich elite who may take decisions which may worsen the position of the poor. Such similar examples can also be given for individuals, gender and households.

Another similar criticism is regarding Sen's version of telos of 'living well' which according to Deneulin and McGregor is considered inadequate and needs to be modified to telos of 'living well together' and includes considerations of the social structures and institutions which enable the people to pursue freedoms in relation to others. Hence greater consideration should be given to the political economy of decision making processes and the manner in which the conflicts and distribution of power are institutionalized. However, the CA is non-partisan and does not advocate a particular ideology like capitalism or socialism. Sen has laid emphasis on humans as ends in themselves and has given more emphasis on the people led process of decision making.

In any case, most of the criticisms appear misplaced when we consider that CA is not a watertight theory in fact, it is only a framework to look at certain issues. Moreover, it is in the process of being further developed.

Conclusion:

The most important contribution of CA is that it places human beings at the centre stage by showing that the overriding objective of development is the expansion of human capabilities rather than economic growth per se. While growth may be necessary for development, it is not always sufficient.

As a policy framework, it is valuable for both developing as well as developed nations since it takes into account their plurality, structural differences, patterns of inequality etc. The approach goes beyond the realm of Economics and incorporates concepts from other social sciences such as Philosophy, Political Science etc. The strength of the approach lies in its flexible and open-ended nature; it incorporates plural concerns and is constructed such that it is a broad framework rather than a precise theory of well-being. It is applied in a variety of fields ranging from development and welfare economics, political philosophy and social policy and is used to answer questions of people's well-being, inequality, poverty, happiness, enabling environment etc. The approach provides a basis for designing and/or evaluating policies especially development policies and social cost-benefit analysis. It is being used in academics for empirical studies and provides foundations for the human development paradigm. For example, borrowing heavily from CA, the Sarkozy Commission Report concludes that what gets measured shapes policy choices and there is a need to shift the focus from a production-oriented measurement system to a broader measure of human progress.

The internal pluralism in CA allows researchers to develop, interpret and apply it in different ways. It is non-partisan and does not advocate a particular ideology such as capitalism, socialism rather it treats humans as ends in themselves. However, more work is required to bring out the policy implications of CA. The advocates of CA are conscious of the limitations of this framework and Sen himself has stated that much work is still left to be done. Therefore we may say that the CA is a continuum of the philosophical postulates of Aristotle, Adam Smith, Karl Marx and even Gandhi for attainment of an ideal society and could provide an environment to minimize conflict situations or fault lines, if not, remove them completely.

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